

Cattle Production System and Breeding Practices in Bena-Tsemay District of South Omo, South-Western Ethiopia

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Abstract:

Lack of updated information on the cattle production system and breeding practices are major challenges to cattle producers and policy makers in Ethiopia. This study was conducted in the Bena-Tsemay district aimed to assess the cattle production systems and breeding practices. The household survey involved interviewing of 150 households of eight purposively selected Kebeles from the three livestock production systems. The collected data from the qualitative parameters were analyzed using non-parametric methods and while the means of the quantitative parameters were analyzed by using One-Way ANOVA using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) (SPSS, version 20). Higher ($P < 0.05$) land size was allocated for crop production in mixed crop-livestock production than agro-pastoral production system while higher ($P < 0.001$) grazing land was allocated in pastoral than agro-pastoral and mixed crop-livestock productions. All households were kept local breed (100%) and majority of the households were acquired their breeding cattle through a gift from relatives (62.83%) and whereas, very few acquired from the local market (10.67%). The respondents of three production systems were reported that the range-land (68.33%), crop residue (19.33%) and range-land and crop residues (12.33%) were used as a source of feed for cattle while, water dug (49.3%), Steady River (25.3%), ponds (14.7%) and river and pond (10.7%) were used as water sources for the cattle. The Trapanosomiasis, Anthrax, Black leg and CBPP were important cattle diseases that hindered cattle production in the study area. The feed shortage, prevalence of diseases and poor genetic potential of indigenous cattle were major cattle production constraints. The results from this study indicated that the cattle production systems and breeding practices were traditional and undeveloped. Therefore, we recommended that the genetic improvement of indigenous cattle breeds, improvements in feeds and feeding system, and strengthening veterinary drug supply service to boost merits from cattle production.

Keywords: Agro-pastoral, Cattle Production, Pastoral, Mixed-crop Livestock

1. Introduction

Ethiopia cattle population was estimated to comprise of 60.39 million [1]. The cattle are amongst the dominant livestock species in Ethiopia for 70–90% of the livestock holding households to sustain the livelihoods of poor communities by generating cash income, serving as source of foods and capital, fulfilling cultural obligations, provide about 68 million tons of organic fertilizer and almost 617 million days of animal traction [2]. However, despite of these economic and social merits, the

cattle production systems are generally extensive and traditional [3, 4]. Thus, the cattle production system largely influenced by reduced availability of communal grazing-lands, insufficient access to improved forage production and feeding systems, poor animal health due to different diseases prevalence and low livestock genetic make-up of local cattle breeds [1, 5, 6]. The Bena-Tseamy district has a huge cattle populations' potential which shares large portions of South Omo Zone and however, the information on cattle production systems, cattle breeds, cattle breeding practice,

cattle feed sources and feeding systems, cattle health service delivery system and cattle production constraints are lacked. Therefore, understanding the cattle production and management practices are imperative to design the appropriate cattle production and management strategies and policies to overwhelm to perceived problems and thus, enhancing the livelihoods of pastoral, agro-pastoral and farmer through improving cattle production systems. Thus, the objectives of the study were (1) to assess the cattle production systems (2) to assess the major cattle production constraints.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Description of Study Area

The study was conducted in Bena-Tseamy district of South Omo Zone, South-western Ethiopia. The Bena-Tseamy district has lied between 5°01' and 5°07' North latitude and 36°38' and 37°07' East longitude in the South Omo Zone. The district is characterized by semi-arid and arid climatic conditions, with mean annual rainfall averaging from 350-838mm in bimodal distribution with the long rainy season from March to June while the

small rains between September and October with an ambient temperature ranging from 26-35°C [7]. The vegetation of the study area is dominated by varying densities of *Acacia*, *Grewia*, and *Solanum* woody species [8, 9]. The dominant type of land-use is agro-pastoralism [9, 10] and more than 48% of the total land area of the district is used for grazing and browsing by cattle and goats, respectively [8]. Rain-fed agriculture is practiced and sorghum, maize, millet, bean, wheat, barley, and vegetables are the major crops grown in the study area [8]. The Bena is one of ethnic group, who live in the higher altitude of Bena-Tseamy district more engaged crop production while the Tseamy is another ethnic group who have been practiced pastoralism and living in the lower altitude area of Bena-Tseamy district have been depending on livestock production [8]. The estimated human population of the Bena-Tseamy district is about 86, 691 of which 44, 591 male and 42,100 are females [11] and whereas, the population of livestock are estimated to be 525, 941 cattle, 211, 818 sheep, 910, 252 goats, 235, 363 Poultry and 36, 387 donkeys [12].

Figure 1. Map of Study Area.

2.2. Study Design

2.2.1. Sample Selection Procedure and Sample Size

A multistage sampling procedure was employed to select study Kebeles. The first stage 34 Kebeles of

Bena-Tseamy district stratified into three based on livestock production systems (Pastoralists, Agro-pastoralists and mixed crop-livestock). In the second stage, purposive sampling technique was employed to select the sample study Kebeles (the lowest

administrative sub-unity) from each production system based on the cattle population and cattle rearing experience. Accordingly, three Kebeles namely Sitemba, Luka and Anesonda from pastoral, four Kebeles namely Argo, Shaba, Gurdo and Sile from the agro-pastoral production system and one kebele (Chali) from mixed crop-livestock production system were purposely selected for face-to-face household interview. Lastly, a simple random sampling technique was employed to select households from each Kebeles that owned cattle. The sample size from each Kebele was determined based on proportion to the total human population in each selected Kebele and thus, a total of 150 households (57 households from pastoral, 55 households from agro-pastoral and 38 households from mixed crop-livestock production system) were selected according to [13] sampling technique.

$$n_o = \frac{Z^2 * (P)(q)}{d^2} \rightarrow n_1 = \frac{n_o}{(1 + n_o / N)}$$

Where, n_o = desired sample size according to Cochran's (1977) when population greater than 10,000; n_1 = finite population correction factors population less than 10,000; Z = standard normal deviation (1.96 for 95% confidence level); P = 0.11 (proportion of population to be included in sample i.e. 11%); q = 1-0.11 i.e. (0.89); d = is degree of accuracy desired (0.05), 5% error term.

2.3.Data Collection Methods

2.3.1. Household Survey

Primary data collected through interviewing the households using semi-structured questionnaires. During the face-to-face interviews, the information gathered were demographic characteristics of the households, landholding, number of cattle owned, and type of livestock they kept, cattle production objectives, cattle production systems, feed resource for cattle, watering, housing, cattle breeding practices, major cattle diseases, veterinary service delivery system and major constraints of cattle production in the study area.

2.3.2. Focus Group Discussion (FGDs)

In each selected Kebele one focus group discussion was conducted by using a checklist prepared for this purpose. The participants in the focus group discussions were comprised of 8-12 interviewees of which about 3-6 were women households. The participants for focus group discussion were drawn from pastoralists, agro-pastoralists, and farmers from crop-livestock

production system by the aid of development agents based on their cattle production experiences. The general information about the cattle production, cattle breeding practices and the major cattle production constraints are key points that were exposed to respondents during the FGDs.

2.4.Methods of Data Analysis

Data collected from the face-to-face survey were entered and managed using the MS excel computer program. The data on qualitative traits were analyzed by using non-parametric methods (chi-square analysis) to describe the various variables on cattle production systems by using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) (SPSS, version 20) while the means of the quantitative parameters were analyzed by using One-Way ANOVA and the significant means were compared by using Duncan's Multiple Range Test and values were considered significant at $P < 0.05$ or 0.001. An index value was calculated as the sum of the weighted number of responses for criterion to provide an overall ranking for qualitative data [14].

$$\text{Index} = \frac{R_n * C_1 + R_{n-1} * C_2 + \dots + R_1 * C_n}{\sum R_n * C_1 + R_{n-1} * C_2 + \dots + R_1 * C_n}$$

Where, R_n = Value given for the least ranked level (if the least rank is 3rd, then $R_n = 3$, $R_{n-1} = 2$, $R_1 = 1$) C_n = Counts of the least ranked level (in the above example, the count of the 3rd rank = C_n , and the count of the 1st rank = C_1).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1.Demography of Households

The demographic characteristics of the interviewed households are presented in Table 1. Majority (80.7%) of the respondents in the study area were male-headed households while 19.3% were female headed. The sex of the respondent was no associated across the livestock production systems ($P > 0.05$). The higher male-headed households involvement in pastoral and agro-pastoral production system from this study for cattle production due to the cultural norms that limited the participation of females in at household level. This is indicated that there is a high gender discrimination practices towards sex in pastoral and agro-pastoral areas. Similar study reported by [15] from the Malle district of South Omo which shown that most of the household heads that are reared

cattle were males headed than female headed due to the societal norms that restrict the females' participation equally with males in the communities. Moreover, the study reported from Afar Eastern Ethiopia showed that the female interactions in community affairs are limited due to numerous cultural restrictions and prohibitions [15]. There was no significant ($P>0.05$) difference observed on the average age and family size of respondents among the pastoral, agro-pastoral and mixed crop-livestock production system. However, respondents of the pastoral production system had longer ($P<0.05$) cattle keeping experience than the agro-pastoralists and mixed crop-livestock producers. The findings

on average age of household from this study for the three livestock production systems showed that majority of the cattle producers in the study area were in the age range of active labor force and it was in agreement with previously reported findings [15, 17]. The overall average family size from the present study was lower than the value (9.65 persons) reported by [15] for Malle district in South Omo and (10 persons) for Borana Pastoralists by [17] but it was higher than the average family size at national level in Ethiopia (5.3 persons) and (5 persons) for South Nations Nationalities and People Regional state, respectively [18].

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of interviewed households in the Bena-Tsemay district of South Omo.

Variables	Production system			Overall (N=150)	(X ²)	P-value
	Pastoral (N = 57)	Agro-pastoral (N = 55)	Crop-Livestock (N = 38)			
Sex of households (%)					0.62	0.73
Male	82.50	81.80	76.30	80.7		
Female	17.50	18.20	23.70	19.3		
Age of HH (Yrs.)					P-value	SL
Average (Means ±SEM)	44±1.22	43± 1.35	47±1.52	45±0.78	0.17	NS
Family Size (P)						
Average (Means ±SEM)	6.4±1.83	6.27±1.6	5.71±1.3	6.19±1.6	0.10	NS
Farming experience (Yrs.)						
Average (Means ±SEM)	31±0.9 ^a	28±0.8 ^b	27±1.0 ^b	29±0.5	<0.001	**

N= Number of sampled households; SEM = Standard error of means; SL = Significance Level; X² = Persons chi-square; HH = Households; P = Person/HH; Yrs. = years; NS = Not significant at $P>0.001$; **= Significant at $P<0.001$.

As presented in Figure 2, most of the households in each cattle production system were illiterate. The finding from this study is not in line with the values reported by different authors. Accordingly, [19] reported that about (41.7%) of Borana pastoralists had attended formal education; [8] reported that about (98.1%) of the Hamer and Bena-Tsemay pastoralists were not acquired any kind of education

and [20] reported about (83.88%) of Hamer pastoralists were illiterate which unable to read and write. However, the findings from this study are relatively similar to the findings reported by [15] from Malle district of South Omo which indicated that about 68.30%, 15%, and 11% of agro-pastoralist were illiterate, read and write and primary school (1-4), respectively.

Figure 2. Education status of interviewed households in Bene-Tsemay district.

3.2. Land holding and use pattern

The average land allocation for the crop production and grazing land are presented in Table 2. The higher ($P < 0.001$) land was allocated for crop production in mixed crop-livestock production than agro-pastoral production system while higher ($P < 0.001$) land was allocated for cattle grazing-land in pastoral production system than agro-pastoral and mixed crop-livestock production while it was insignificant ($P > 0.001$) between agro-pastoral and mixed crop-livestock production systems. The higher land is allocated for crop cultivation in the in mixed crop-livestock production system than agro-pastoral production system is due to the farmers are extensively conveyed on the cultivation of the major crops. The average land allocated for crop production per household found from present study

was below the average nationally reported value of (1.77ha) [21] and however, it was higher than previously reported average value of (0.8ha) by [15] for Malle district in South Omo. On the other hand, the result on average land allocated for a cattle grazing per household is higher in pastoral production as compared to agro-pastoral and mixed crop-livestock production area is because the population distribution in the pastoral area is less dense and therefore, this is allowed communities to allocate more lands for grazing-land as compared to agro-pastoral and mixed crop-livestock production systems. The result on average land allocated for grazing-land of this study was higher than values of (0.23ha) and (0.36ha) per household reported for Malle district of South Omo Zone [15].

Table 2. Average Land holding and land use pattern of the households (Mean \pm SEM) in the Bena-Tsemay district.

Average land allocations	Cattle Production system			Overall (N=150)	P-value
	Pastoral (N=57)	Agro-pastoral (N=55)	Crop-livestock (N=38)		
Crop production (ha)					
Average (Mean \pm SE)	-	0.85 ^a \pm 0.06	1.03 ^b \pm 0.05	0.68 \pm 0.04	0.001***
Grazing land (ha)					
Average (Mean \pm SE)	4.54 ^b \pm 0.25	2.87 ^a \pm 0.14	2.53 ^a \pm 0.17	3.42 \pm 0.14	0.001***

N = number of respondents; SEM = standard error of Means; Means with different superscripts (a, b) within a row are significantly different at $P < 0.001$; *** = Significant at $P < 0.001$.

3.3. Livestock species compositions

The average numbers of livestock species composition in the study area are presented in Table 3. Higher ($P < 0.001$) number of cattle and goat were found in pastoral and agro-pastoral production systems than and mixed crop-livestock production system while the average goat numbers were not-significantly varied ($P > 0.001$) between pastoral and agro-pastoral production systems. The more number of cattle and goats per household in the pastoral production system than agro-pastoral and crop-livestock production systems is due to the suitability of the agro-ecology for rearing cattle and goats.

The average number of cattle, goat, and sheep owned by Bena-Tsemay households from this study were lower than previously reported values of (46), (75) and (45) for cattle, goat and sheep, respectively for the same study area [8] and however, it was higher than the values (12.30, 16.40 and 7) reported by [15] from Malle district of South Omo, respectively. The other studies reported from Borana Ethiopia showed that an average cattle holding per household is (24.14) by [22] and (22.57) by [23] which is relatively comparable to overall average value obtained from the present study.

Table 3. Livestock species composition (Mean \pm SEM) of the households in Bena-Tsemay district.

Livestock species (Means \pm SEM)	Cattle Production systems			Overall (N=150)	SL
	Pastoral (N=57)	Agro-pastoral (N=55)	Crop-livestock (N=38)		
Cattle	32.28 \pm 2.63 ^a	20.38 \pm 1.30 ^b	12.50 \pm 1.28 ^c	22.91 \pm 1.32	***
Sheep	23.67 \pm 2.24	19.20 \pm 1.75	17.03 \pm 1.82	20.35 \pm 1.17	NS
Goats	28.77 \pm 2.07 ^a	23.18 \pm 2.90 ^a	15.74 \pm 2.09 ^b	23.42 \pm 1.32	***
Poultry	8.40 \pm 0.36	9.15 \pm 0.61	9.05 \pm 0.61	8.84 \pm 0.30	NS

Donkeys	4.60±0.30	3.67±0.27	2.97±0.30	3.85±0.17	NS
Beehives	8.46 ^a ±0.36	6.73 ^b ±0.38	6.42 ^b ±0.4	7.31±0.24	***

N = number of respondents; SEM = standard error of Means; Means with different superscripts (a, b, c) within a row are significantly different at P< 0.001; SL = Significance Level; *** = Significant at P<0.001

3.4. Purpose of keeping cattle

The purposes of keeping cattle in the study area are presented in Table 4. The households in pastoral production system have kept cattle primarily for milk and milk products and followed by income source and cultural values and however, there are no any pastoralists that have kept cattle for draft power. Likewise, in the agro-pastoral production system, households also have kept cattle primarily for milk and milk products and followed by income source, cultural value, and draft power. Similarly reports of [15] and [24] were demonstrated that herders of Malle and Mursi districts of South Omo have been primordially raised cattle for milk and milk products followed by income, draft power and dowry. However, in the mixed crop-livestock production systems, households have kept cattle primarily for draft power and followed by milk and milk products, income sources, and cultural values. During the focus group discussion, respondents of pastoral and agro-pastoral systems were mentioned that cow milk and milk products play an important role in family nutrition in addition to income generation sources. Also respondents from mixed crop- livestock production system were reported that milk and milk product is used as an income source due to milk is processed into butter which is sold at the local market to generate additional income. Additionally, respondents were mentioned that in the pastoral areas where the crop farming activities are not practiced and the cattle have played a vital role in securing cultural values and persons with a large number of cattle is an indication of wealthiest in the communities and hence, they have kept more cattle. In support to result from the present study, the previous studies reported by [10] and [8] were also confirmed that the pastoral production system of South Omo traditionally has been based on cattle husbandry for milk production and wealth storage. In the mixed crop-livestock production system cattle are primarily kept for draft power is due to the crop farming activity needs oxen as a source of traction. In supports to result from the present study, a study reported by [23] from Southern Ethiopia had showed that the lowland residents of Borana were

gave more attention to bulls for the market to increase their income and whereas, the mid-highland population probably needed the oxen as a source of draught power for crop production.

Table 4. Purpose of Cattle Rearing in Bena-Tsemay district.

Production system	Purpose cattle rearing	Index	Rank
Pastoral	Milk and milk product	0.40	1
	Income source	0.33	2
	Cultural value	0.27	3
	Draft power	-	-
Agro-pastoral	Milk and milk product	0.30	1
	Income source	0.23	2
	Cultural value	0.25	3
	Draft power	0.22	4
Crop livestock	Milk and milk product	0.26	2
	Income source	0.24	3
	Cultural value	0.21	4
	Draft power	0.27	1

Index=sum of all single-purpose rank [(4 for 1) + (3 for 2) + (2 for 3) + (1 for 4)] divided by the sum of all weighed purposes of livestock rearing mentioned by respondents.

3.5. Cattle Breeds and Breeding Practices

The cattle breeds been kept by respondents in the three production systems of the study area are indicated in Figure 3. All cattle breed kept by herders were local cattle (mixture of Hamar and Boran breeds). However, none of the households in the study area were kept neither exotic nor crossbreed. During the focus group discussion with respondents, they were mentioned that the main reason of keeping local breeds is due to the survivability potential of local cattle on poor grazing condition, have high potential to resist diseases and pest and can walk long distance in search of water and pasture during dry seasons as compared to exotic cattle. In agreement with the present study, [25] had reported that the Dassench pastoral community of South Omo kept only the local breeds of cattle. Similarly, it has been also reported that from the total cattle that have been reared in Ethiopian about 98.24% of cattle are indigenous genotypes [1]. The major sources of cattle for breeding purposes in the study area are displayed in Figure 4. Majority of the households in the three

livestock production systems acquired their breeding cattle through a gift from relatives and while very few of them inherited their breeding animals from owned family and purchase from the local market. The majority of households in the study acquired breeding cattle from relatives is due to the culture of contributing cattle from relatives in the form of gift

or loan for young men who engaged newly in marriage to establish his newly own family. Similarly, [26] report was verified that the pastoralists in Western and Central Uganda acquired their breeding cattle from relegated births, inherited and bought from the local market.

Figure 3. Type of cattle breed reared in Bena-Tsema.

Figure 4. Major sources of cattle for breeding purposes.

The sources of cattle for stock replacement in the study area are displayed in Figure 5. The result indicated that majority of households of pastoral and agro-pastoral production systems were acquired stock replacing animal by purchasing from the local market and however, others were acquired from both owned herd and purchase from the local market. However, in mixed crop-livestock production system, the few interviewees had acquired stocking animals from owned herds only.

Generally, during the focus group discussion with respondents, they were mentioned that the inheritance and social networks in form of gifts are major sources to acquire their replacing herds. In supports to result from present study, [27] reported that majority of pastoralists replace their breeding stock from their own herds, from neighbors, friends or relatives and from local markets.

Figure 5. Source of cattle for stock replacement in Bena-Tsemay district of South Omo.

3.6. Source of Breeding Bull

The sources for breeding bull reported in the study area are presented in Table 5. In the study area, majority households of pastoral and agro-pastoral production systems were reported that they were possessed breeding bull and however, very few of households had reported that they had no possessed breeding bull. During the focus group discussion with desiccants, the respondents who did not owned the breeding bull is due to they have been practiced herding practice in the communal grazing-land where their cows can be mated by their

neighbors' bulls. However, all respondents from crop-livestock production system possessed the breeding bull and they were mentioned that their majority of cattle have grazed on privately owned grazing pasture-land and where their herds are rarely mated with others herds so that they were owned their breeding bulls. Similarly, [24] reported that most of the Borana pastoralists in lowland and mid-highland areas of Southern Ethiopia possessed the breeding bulls which have potential to produce superior progenies.

Table 5. Source of breeding bull in the Bena-Tsemay district, in South Omo Zone, south-western Ethiopia.

Particulars	Production System				X ²	P-value
	Pastoral (N= 57)	Agro-pastoral (N= 55)	Crop-livestock (N= 38)	Over all (N= 150)		
Do you have source for breeding bull (%)?					0.1	0.22
Yes	85.62	92.15	100	92.59		
No	14.48	7.85	-	7.41		
Source of breeding bull (%)					6.05	0.13
Own herd	68.40	45.50	55.30	56.70		
Neighbor herd only	-	-	-	-		
Owned and neighbor herd	31.60	54.50	44.70	43.30		

The value observed between the three production system are not significantly different at * ($X^2 > 0.05$); $X^2 =$ Pearson Chi-square; N= Number of respondents

3.7. Selection criteria for breeding bull

As presented in Table 6 all households of the three production systems have their own selection criteria for breeding bull. The majority of households of pastoral and agro-pastoral were selected breeding bull based on bulls body size, growth rate and coat color from their owned herds and whereas, few of respondents were based on the

growth rate and body weight of bulls. During focus group discussions in three cattle production systems, respondents were replied that animals that have large body size and fast growing potential have high grazing capacity and early attained marketable weight and hence, they were earned the high immediate cash needs for children school fees, medical bills which usually requires large sums of

money. The study reported by [15] reveals that agro-pastoralists from Malle district in South Omo were selected breeding bull mainly based on body size followed by coat color and growth rate which is concurred to the result from present study. Moreover, the bull/steers with fast growth rate mature early and can be used for draftability at an early age and hence are more economical when compared to their slow growing counterparts [28]. However, few respondents of pastoral, agro-pastoral and crop-livestock selected breeding bull based on coat color. They are reasoned that bulls with whole or dominantly black colors not preferred by the communities due to the black colors have attracted the more heat and tsetse-fly which is responsible for death of animals. They also mentioned that coat

colors is very important criteria during breeding time due to fact that they correlated coat colors with marketing value of cattle. They were reported that animals with brown or red colors are more preferred colors by herders and whereas, bulls with whole or dominantly black colors are not preferred by herders due to their low marketing value. Similarly, [15] reported that the coat color of the bulls is an important criteria during selection the bulls for breeding in pastoral and agro-pastoral areas which they may be ascribed to socio cultural preferences and economic value. Also [23] was reported that pastoral community from Borana lowland areas emphasized the size of the animal, color of the animal and pedigree as the first, second and third criteria of selection during breeding bull selection.

Table 6. Selection criteria for breeding bull in Bena-Tsemay district of South Omo, South-western-Ethiopia.

Variables	Production System				X ²	P-vale
	Pastoral (N= 57)	Agro-pastoral (N= 55)	Crop-livestock (N= 38)	Over all (N= 150)		
Do you have criteria for breeding bulls' selection (%)?					0.56	
Yes	100	100	100	100		
No	-	-	-	-		
Selection criteria for breeding bulls (%)					0.23	<0.001
Boy size	1.80	-	-	0.70		
Growth rate	-	-	-	-		
Coat color	31.60	23.60	23.70	26.70		
Body size and growth rate	22.80	18.20	55.30	29.30		
Body size, growth rate and coat color	43.90	58.20	21.10	43.30		

The value observed between the three cattle production system significantly different at *** p <0.001; X²= Pearson Chi-square; N = Number of respondents

Figure 6. Selection criteria for heifers in the Bena-Tsemay district.

3.8. Selection Criteria for Breeding Heifer

The selection criteria for breeding heifer in the

study area for three production system are displayed in Figure 6. The result was demonstrated that most

of interviewees from three production systems had their own selection criteria for breeding heifers. The respondents' mainly select breeding heifer based on growth rate (wider face, long legs, and wider udder) and milk production traits (based mother's performance history). However, few respondents from three farming systems select breeding heifer based milk production trait (based mothers performance history). In support to findings from this study, the study reported from Borana lowland area by [23] was shown that the Borana pastoralists select breeding females mainly based on milk yield and growth performance.

3.9.Source of Feeds for Cattle

As shown in Figure 7, natural pastures from range-land are major feed sources (pasture grasses, legumes and shrubs) for cattle in the study area. The households of agro-pastoral and mixed crop-livestock production system were also used crop residue mainly from maize and sorghum in addition to natural pasture as a source of feed for cattle. According to the response of households during the group discussion they were mainly provided leaves of browse trees and shrubs to milking cows, calves,

sick and aged cattle not able to move in long distance to search pasture and water during complete dry seasons from the January to February. In addition, the maize Stover also used as a cattle feed in crop-livestock farming system and however, the crop residues is poorly utilized by cattle since producers collect and store it outside in an open area and provided to cattle as it is without chopping and/or treatment during critical dry seasons as feed shortage mitigation strategies. In agreement with the present study, the study reported from the pastoral areas of Mursi, Bena-Tsemay, Hamer, Malle and Dassench were indicated that major feed source for livestock comes from range-land [8, 15, 24, 25, 29, 30]. Similarly, similar feed sources were reported from Borana range-lands of Southern Ethiopia [22]. Moreover, [10] report had demonstrated that some agro-pastoral households in Bena-Tsemay and Hamer districts listed crop residues mainly from *Zea mays* (L) and *Sorghum bicolor* harvests as livestock feed resources next to natural pasture from range-land which is in line with result from the present study.

Figure 7. Major feed resources used by cattle in Bena-Tsemay district.

Figure 8. Percentage of cattle feeding system practiced by households in Bena-Tsemay district.

3.10. Cattle feeding system

The cattle feeding system in the study area is presented in Figure 8. Cattle free grazing on range-land forage is the common cattle feeding system have been practicing in the study area. However, very few (11.25%) households from the mixed crop-livestock production system feeding their cattle by tether on privately owned pasture-land (enclosed areas). The reason for free grazing feeding system have been practicing by majority of the households in the study area is due to the large number of cattle owned by households makes it difficult for tethering and stall-feeding system. Similarly, [24] and [25] reported that cattle feeding system in Salamago and

Dassench districts in South Omo is free grazing on communal grazing-land but some pastoral communities in the Mursi area have been practicing both free grazing and tethering, for cattle that could not move long distances, such as calves which are usually tethered on pasture-land near to the homestead.

3.11. Cattle supplementation practice

The Table 7 below showed that majority of respondents (75.3%) of pastoral, agro-pastoral and mixed crop-livestock production system were supplemented their milking cows, calves, and sick animal with leaf of browse species such as different acacia species and very few (4%) respondents of mixed crop-livestock system were supplemented cattle with hay, crop residues and Banana leaf during dry seasons. However, in the study area the supplementation of cattle with commercial concentrates is not familiar in three livestock production systems. This is due to all households were stated that commercial concentrate is unaffordable to them due to it is not available and they have possessed the large cattle numbers which is impractical to provide commercial concentrate supplements. Similarly, the previously reported studies were showed that the pastoral and agro pastoral communities of Hamer, Bena-Tsemay, Dassench, Mursi and Malle had no supplemented their livestock with commercial supplements due to unaffordability of commercial concentrate but some area the model agro-pastoralists have traditionally fatten their indigenous cattle with locally available feeds such as leaf and pods from different browse species and pumpkin after grazing [8, 10, 20, 29, 30]

Table 7. Feed sources used as supplements for cattle in Bena-Tsemay district.

Variables	Production System			Over all (N=150)	X ²	(P-value)
	Pastoral (N= 57)	Agro- pastoral (N= 55)	Crop-livestock (N= 38)			
Supplements					1.42	0.64
Hay and crop residues	-	27.30	23.70	16.00		
Concentrated feeds	-	-	-	-		
Hay, crop residues and Banana leaf	-	-	15.80	4.00		
Browse trees and <i>Attela</i>	-	-	18.40	4.70		
Browse trees leafs	100	72.70	42.10	75.30		

The value observed between the three production system are not significantly different at P> 0.001; X²= Pearson Chi-square; N = sampled households.

3.12. Coping strategies to feed shortage

The coping strategies to cattle feed shortage by households in the study area are presented in Figure 9.

According to the present study, seasonal migration and stock division were used as the main copying strategy to feed shortage by majority of the

households (45.3%). The households of pastoral and agro-pastoral production system used seasonal mobility as the main strategy during the critical feed shortage during dry seasons particularly in the month of January and February. They mostly moved their cattle to the big rivers such as Woyito, Mago or Omo in search of feed and water. On the other hand majority (55.30%) of the farmers in the crop-livestock production system used feed preservation as a coping strategy to feed shortage. The other pastoral and agro-pastoralists households were also engaged division of cattle into calf, aged and sick cattle and graze near to the homestead in enclosures. In agreement with the present study, [30] reported that agro-pastoralists' communities in the Malle district have been moving their cattle to the area where surplus pasture available such as Daramalo in Gamgofa Zone and Maze Park then back to their home when the pasture conditions will be secured. Also [8] and [20] were reported that the Hamer and

Bena pastoralists have mobilized their cattle toward the Mago park during the recurrent drought and deterioration of grazing- lands, respectively. Similarly, the Mursi and Dumi pastoral and agro-pastoral of Salamago district in South Omo were moved their herds to Omo, Mersiyo and Sherma river, Bize and Hindo valley, where grass is thought to be more available during the critical feed shortages and back to residence area when feed availability is secured [20]. Moreover, the supplementation of cattle with locally available browse species during dry season is common practice of few households (19.30%) in pastoral and agro-pastoral production system as coping strategies to the feed shortage in the study area. Similar studies were reported from the South Omo which were demonstrated that pastoralist communities are supplemented their lactating cow, sick animals, kids and lambs with leaves and pods of browse species during dry seasons as coping mechanism to feed shortage [8, 10, 20, 29, 30].

Figure 9. Percentage of coping strategies to feed shortage in Bena-Tsemay district of South Omo, South-western Ethiopia.

3.13. Water source for cattle

The water sources for cattle in the study area are presented in Figure 10. The finding from this study demonstrated that there are three water sources (Water dug, steady river and ponds) are used for the cattle in the study area. Majority households of pastoral and agro-pastoral production system were used water dug as water source for cattle and whereas, the steady river mostly used in mixed crop-livestock production system. The respondents of pastoral and agro-pastoral were mentioned that water dug which is called locally “Chiroshi” which means water acquired from sand after deep digging is common water source for cattle in the study area especially dry seasons. On the other hand, few

(25.30%) households of pastoral and agro-pastoral production system also reported that pond water is common water source for cattle. The respondents were mentioned that during the critical dry seasons, pastoralists and agro-pastoral households moved cattle to the big rivers such as Omo and Woyito in search of water and grazing pasture. This is due to ponds are easily accessed and available for short periods but the water dugs are usually a permanent,, however it is required a large forces to lift water from the depth. Similar to the results from the present study, [8] reported that majority of the Hamer, Bena and Tsemay pastoralists used water from rivers (Kako and Woyito), while very few of the pastoralists used water from ponds and

Boreholes. Moreover, [15] reported that the agro-pastoralists from Malle district were used steady-river (97.25%) and pond/catchments (2.5%) for the cattle.

Figure 10. Percentage of water sources for cattle in Bena-Tsema district of South Omo, South-western Ethiopia.

3.14. Cattle house and housing system

As indicated in Table 8, all households from the three livestock production system housed their cattle. Pertaining to house type, the dominant housing types commonly used for cattle in the three production system was Kraals (86.70%) and while, few (13.30%) respondents of mixed crop-livestock production system were used enclosed barn which is made from the local available materials without upper protecting cover from sun/rain. During the focus group discussion and field observation in study area, the Kraals houses type was constructed by using locally available materials and all respondents were replied that they separately housed their cattle based on age

category in Kraals at whole night time. They mentioned that cattle such as calves and sick animals were housed in Kraal by separating from the other herds while, the other class of cattle such as cows; heifers and bulls were housed together in Kraal. The result of the current study was consistent with [31] who reported that majority (94.70%) of pastoralists housed their cattle in open constructed barn (Kraals) at night in Borena Zone of Southern Ethiopia. Similarly, the study reported by [32] showed that the cattle in the lowland areas were housed in the Kraal's which however provides limited protection against the natural calamities and the predators.

Table 8. Type of house and housing system for cattle in the Bena-Tsema district of South Omo, South-western Ethiopia

Particulars	Production System				X ²	P-value
	Pastoral (N = 57)	Agro-pastoral (N = 55)	Crop-livestock (N = 38)	Over all (N = 150)		
Do you house cattle?					1.42	0.06NS
Yes	100	100	100	100		
No	-	-	-	-		
Type of house					1.23	<0.01*
Kraals	100	100	47.40	86.70		
In living rooms	-	-	-	-		
Enclosed barn	-	-	52.60	13.30		
Housing System					6.7	1.08NS
Separately housed in Kraals	100	100	100	100		
Housed with other animals in Corral	-	-	-	-		
Living with human	-	-	-	-		

The value observed between the three production system are not significantly different at $p < 0.05$; $X^2 =$ Pearson Chi-square; $N =$ Number of respondents; $NS =$ Non-significant.

Table 9. Ranks of major diseases among the cattle reared in the Bena-Tsema district of South Omo Zone, South-western Ethiopia

Cattle production system	Major diseases	Index	Rank
Pastoral	Anthrax	0.26	2 nd
	Black leg	0.25	3 rd
	Trypanosomosis	0.27	1 st
	CBPP	0.22	4 th
Agro-pastoral	Black leg	0.26	2 nd
	Anthrax	0.23	3 rd
	Trypanosomosis	0.27	1 st
	CBPP	0.22	4 th
Crop-livestock	Anthrax	0.19	4 th
	Black leg	0.30	1 st
	Trypanosomosis	0.22	3 rd
	CBPP	0.27	2 nd

3.15. Major Cattle Diseases

The major cattle diseases in the study area are presented in Table 9. According to the respondents, there are four major cattle diseases that have been hindered the cattle production in Bena-Tsemay district. Accordingly, Trypanosomosis was ranked as 1st in pastoral and agro-pastoral system while blackleg was ranked 1st in crop livestock production system as an important cattle disease that mainly affecting the livelihoods through hindering the cattle production in the study area. During the focus group discussion with participants of pastoral and agro-pastoral systems, they were mentioned that cattle infected with Trypanosomosis frequently show symptom of rising of hair and depression especially during wet season. This might be due to the area where their cattle have been grazing is tsetse suppression and has been greatly confronted the cattle production system. They also mentioned that even though Anthrax is major cattle diseases that has affected development of livestock production, but in the pastoral and agro-pastoral areas, it is less important because of the fewer occurrences some times in the binging of main rain seasons. Similarly, [24] who reported that Trypanosomosis, blackleg, anthrax and CCBP were the major diseases that leads major challenges to cattle production in the Mursi and Bodi pastoral areas in South Omo Zone. Moreover, the study reported by [15] was indicated that the blackleg (1st) is the most common diseases affecting cattle production in lowland agro-ecology of Malle district which is relatively comparable to results reported by households of mixed crop-livestock production system from the present study.

3.16. Cattle Veterinary Delivery Services

The access to animal health services, services delivering organization and distance to the health service center reported by the interviewees are presented in Table 10. All respondents were replied that they have access to animal health services in the study area. Majority of respondents used animal health services delivered by government while very few (11.06%) of respondents of agro-pastoral and mixed crop-livestock only use private veterinary clinic to treat their cattle. Pertaining to the distance to veterinary service center, the respondents from the pastoral production system reported that they were traveled longer ($P < 0.001$) distance to get animal veterinary services than respondent of agro-pastoral and mixed crop-livestock production systems. However, the respondents from the mixed crop-livestock production system have been acquired animal veterinary services from the shorter distance ($P < 0.001$) from their homestead as compared to respondents from agro-pastoral production systems. Similar to result from the present study, the study reported by [31] from the Southern Ethiopia (Borana) was demonstrated that pastoralists were used veterinary service delivered by government clinic, private clinic, traditional medications services, government and private clinic in order to treat their cattle from the diseases and parasites. Contrary to the result from the present study, [33] reported that due to establishment of health centers in nearby Kebeles, farmers access veterinary service within 5km distance in Bure areas.

Table 10. The type of veterinary service and distance to veterinary service center in Bena-Tsemay district of South Omo Zone, South-western Ethiopia

Particulars	Production system			Over all (N=150)	X ²	P- value
	Pastoral (N= 57)	Agro-pastoral (N= 55)	Crop-livestock			

				(N= 38)	
Access to veterinary service?					
Yes	100	100	100	100	
No	-	-	-	-	
Type of Veterinary Service					19.4 <0.001
Government	45.60	34.50	63.20	47.76	
Private	-	16.40	16.80	11.06	
Government and private	54.40	49.10	20.00	41.17	
Distance travelled for veterinary service (Km)					P-value <0.001
(Mean+ SEM)	2.59 ^a ±0.13	2.09 ^b ± 0.09	1.94 ^c ± 0.12	2.24±0.1	SL ***

The three cattle production system are significantly different at $p < 0.001$; $X^2 =$ Pearson Chi-square; N = number of respondents; SEM = Standard error of means; Km = Kilometer

3.17. Constraints of Cattle Production

The cattle production constraints ranked by interviewed households in the study area are presented in Table 11. According to the respondents from the pastoral production system, feed shortage is the major constraint ranked as 1st followed by prevalence of diseases, poor genetic potential and poor extension services. Conversely, in the agro-pastoral production system, respondents were ranked that feed shortage is the major cattle production constraint ranked as 1st which was followed by poor genetic potential, poor extension services and prevalence of diseases. However, in mixed crop-livestock production system, respondents were ranked shortage of land for cattle grazing as 1st production constraint followed by feed shortage, prevalence of diseases and poor extension services. According to group discussants, cattle largely depend on range-land grazing or crop residues which is not uniformly supplied and poor its nutritive value. There is a seasonal fluctuation in the availability and quality of feed has been a common phenomenon, which are induced serious changes in cattle production. Similar to result from the present study, the studies reported by different scholars in South Omo were confirmed that feed shortage is major constraint that have been affected cattle production through making cattle to delay in puberty and thereafter adversely influence the production and reproduction capability of the cattle [8, 24, 25, 29, 30]. Moreover, [34-38] reports were showed that shortage of land, shortage of feed, prevalence of disease, capacity gap and weak extension services and low genetic potential of local animals for functional traits are identified as a major constraints threatening

cattle production in different part of Ethiopia.

Table 11. Ranks of constraints for cattle production in Bena-Tsemay district of south Omo, Sout-western, Ethiopia.

Production system	Constraints for cattle production	Index	Rank
Pastoral	Poor genetic potential	0.24	3
	Shortage of Feed	0.28	1
	Prevalence of disease and parasites	0.25	2
	Poor extension service	0.23	4
Agro-pastoral	Poor genetic potential	0.26	2
	Shortage of feed	0.27	1
	Prevalence of disease and parasites	0.22	4
	Poor extension service	0.25	3
Crop-livestock	Shortage of land	0.27	1
	Shortage of feed	0.26	2
	Prevalence of disease and parasites	0.25	3
	Poor extension service	0.22	4

Index=sum of all single-purpose rank [(4 for 1) + (3 for 2) + (2 for 3) + (1 for 4)] divided by the sum of all weighed purposes of livestock rearing mentioned by respondents

4. Conclusion and Recommendation

The result from this study was showed that the pastoral, agro-pastoral and crop-livestock production systems were major farming system and all respondents of pastoral and agro-pastoral were extensively kept the indigenous cattle breed mainly for milk and milk products and followed by income source and cultural values and however, in the mixed crop-livestock production systems, cattle are kept primarily for draft power and tracked by milk and milk products, income sources and cultural value. The range-land is

major feed sources for cattle in the three production systems and however, the crop residues are used as cattle feed source in mixed crop-livestock production system next to rangeland. The cattle feeding, watering, housing, animal health delivery system and breeding practices in the study area were outdated. The shortage of feeds, prevalence of diseases, poor genetic potential and extension services are major cattle production constraints in the study area. Based on the findings of this study, we recommended that genetic improvement of indigenous breeds, development of improved forage species and forage banking system, collaborative efforts in using either chemical or physical methods to improve crop residues quality, preparation and utilization of home-made concentrate and strengthening veterinary services through participation of both public and private sectors.

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